

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KALUME****FIRST NAME: BERTIN****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 12%

The author used the following software: (Office 365 on Windows 10)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What are the reasons for mentioning sources in any work of scientific research?
 - (1) Plagiarism is wrong and unethical, (2) it is not fair to take someone's work and not give them credit, (3) and it is a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences.¹**
 - (1) Plagiarism is wrong but not unethical, (2) it is not fair to take someone's work and not give them credit, (3) and it is a serious academic offence that can have serious consequences.

¹ Laurent Cleenwerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

- (1) Plagiarism is wrong and unethical but unavoidable in the case of an extensive research paper, (2) it is not fair to take someone's work and not give them credit, (3) and it is a serious academic offence that can have serious consequences.
 - (1) Plagiarism is wrong and unethical, (2) Under certain circumstances, taking someone's work and not giving them credit is unfair, (3) and it is a serious academic offence that can have serious consequences.
2. List in order the main chapters of writing an essay.
- An introduction, a body, and a conclusion.²**
 - An introduction, a literature review, and a conclusion
 - An introduction, the methodology, and the conclusion
 - An introduction, the collection of data, and the conclusion
3. What are the main advantages of using the WHO's house style?
- (1) The house style increases WHO's credibility, (2) the house style helps WHO to present a single, cohesive image to readers, and (3) the house style benefits WHO staff and streamlines and increases the efficiency of the writing and editing process.³**

² Cleenwerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack*, 10.

³ WHO. *WHO Style Guide*. Second Edition (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013), 7.

- (1) The house style helps WHO to present a single, cohesive image to readers, (2) the house style is easy to use and does not require prior training, and (3) the house style increases WHO's credibility.
 - (1) The House style increases WHO's credibility, (2) The House style is compulsorily recommended for all United Nations Agencies, including the WHO, and (3) The House style is the best-seen style.
 - (1) The house style is the best-seen style, (2) The house style benefits WHO staff, and (3) The house style is easy to use and does not require prior training.
4. List in order the main components of any research proposal.
- An introduction, a literature review, the methodology with data collection and analysis methods, and additional elements include a title, a tentative chapter outline of the dissertation, a projected timetable, and references.⁴**
 - An introduction, the background of the study, the problem statement, the purpose statement, the research questions, the methodology, the research approach, and the study's rationale.
 - An introduction, the background of the study, the problem statement, the research questions, and the methodology.
 - An introduction, a problem statement, a purpose statement, a collection of data, and a conclusion.

⁴ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe. *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth Edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications Inc., 2019), 204-211.

5. List in order the main components of the methodology chapter.

(1) **The research question, (2) the research design, (3) the researcher's background, beliefs, and biases, (4) the population, participants, and sampling technique, (5) the procedures, namely the step-by-step process of collecting data, the difference between qualitative data collection and research approach, and the mention of data characteristics, (6) the data Processing, and (7) the quality assurance in terms of credibility, transferability, and dependability.**⁵

(1) The research question, (2) the quality assurance in terms of credibility, transferability, and dependability, (3) the researcher's background, beliefs, and biases, (4) the population, participants, and sampling technique, (5) the procedures, namely the step-by-step process of collecting data, the difference between qualitative data collection and research approach, and the mention of data characteristics, (6) the data processing, and (7) the research design.

(1) The research question, (2) the researcher's Background, beliefs, and biases, (3) the population, participants, and sampling technique, (4) the procedures, namely the step-by-step process of collecting data, the difference between qualitative data collection and research approach, and the mention of data characteristics, (5) the research design, (6) the data Processing, (7) the quality assurance in terms of credibility, transferability, and dependability.

⁵ Philip Adu. *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study*. YouTube Video, 7 March 2016, 1:05:16, accessed 20 April 2023, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708>.

- (1) The research question, (2) the research design, (3) the researcher's Background, beliefs, and biases, (4) the population, participants, and sampling technique, (5) the data Processing, (6) the quality assurance in terms of credibility, transferability, and dependability, and (7) the procedures, namely the step-by-step process of collecting data, the difference between qualitative data collection and research approach, and the mention of data characteristics.

6. Give the main advantages of using the software called "Grammarly".

- (1) Grammarly helps your writing with style, clarity, and sentence structure, (2) it supports streamlined and effective writing, (3) its suggestions help identify and replace complicated sentences with efficient ones, (4) it refreshes repetitive language, and (5) uphold accurate spelling, punctuation, and grammar.⁶**

- (1) Grammarly helps your writing with style, clarity, and sentence structure, (2) it supports streamlined and effective writing, (3) its suggestions help identify and replace complicated sentences with efficient ones, (4) and it refreshes repetitive language; although it can not uphold accurate spelling, punctuation, and grammar.

- (1) Grammarly helps your writing with style, clarity, and sentence structure, (2) it supports streamlined and effective writing, (3) its suggestions help identify and replace complicated sentences with efficient ones, although it can not refresh repetitive language, and (5) uphold accurate spelling, punctuation, and grammar.

⁶ Ellory Wells. *Grammarly: How Good Is It and Is It Worth the Money?* YouTube Video, 15 November 2015, 21:47, accessed 20 April 2023, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WSaOClkpwP4&t=14s>.

- (1) Grammarly helps your writing with style, clarity, and sentence structure, (2) it supports streamlined and effective writing, although its suggestions can not help identify and replace complicated sentences with efficient ones, (4) it refreshes repetitive language, and (5) uphold accurate spelling, punctuation, and grammar.

7. What are the referencing systems recommended by the WHO?

- The Numerical referencing system and the Harvard referencing system.**⁷
- The American Psychological Association (APA) referencing system, the Chicago referencing system, and the Harvard referencing system.
- The Modern Humanities Research Association (MHRA) referencing and Numerical systems.
- The Modern Language Association of America (MLA) and Chicago referencing systems.

8. Regarding the ethical considerations of any research study, give the safeguards to ensure the protection and rights of participants.

- (1) Informed consent, (2) the participants' rights and interests, (3) confidentiality of names and other significant characteristics, (4) the anonymity of participants, (5) the pseudonyms' assignment or usage, and (6) the storage's security of research-related records and data.**⁸

⁷ WHO, *WHO Style Guide*, 42-43.

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation*, 514.

- (1) Informed consent, (2) the participants' rights and interests, (3) confidentiality of names and other significant characteristics, (4) the anonymity of participants, (5) the pseudonyms' assignment or usage, and (6) the participants' residential addresses.
 - (1) Informed consent, (2) the participants' rights and interests, (3) confidentiality of names and other significant characteristics, (4) the civil status of participants, (5) the pseudonyms' assignment or usage, and (6) the storage's security of research-related records and data.
 - (1) Informed consent, (2) the participants' rights and interests, (3) the level of study or education of the participants, (4) the anonymity of participants, (5) the pseudonyms' assignment or usage, and (6) the storage's security of research-related records and data.
9. List in order the fundamental components of any abstract of a research work-study.
- (1) The title of your study, (2) the research problem, (3) the qualitative research tradition, (4) the theoretical basis, (5) the data sources, (6) the methods and procedures of data collection and analysis, (7) the key findings, (8) the conclusion and recommendations, and (9) the list of keywords.⁹**
 - (1) The title of your study, (2) the research problem, (3) the qualitative research tradition, (4) the theoretical basis, (5) the data sources, (6) the methods and procedures of data collection and analysis, (7) the conclusion and recommendations, (8) the key findings, and (9) the list of keywords.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation*, 68-69; 715-718.

- (1) The title of your study, (2) the data sources, (3) the qualitative research tradition, (4) the theoretical basis, (5) the research problem, (6) the methods and procedures of data collection and analysis, (7) the key findings, (8) the conclusion and recommendations, and (9) the list of keywords.
 - (1) The title of your study, (2) the qualitative research tradition, (3) the theoretical basis, (4) the data sources, (5) the research problem, (6) the methods and procedures of data collection and analysis, (7) the key findings, (8) the list of keywords, and (9) the conclusion and recommendations.
10. What are the most common citation forms covered in the Book “A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Styles for Students and Researchers?”
- The author-date style and the notes style.¹⁰**
 - The author-date style and the numerical style.
 - The notes style and the numerical style.
 - The author-date style, the numerical style, and the notes style.
11. Give in order an outline of the main chapters in each typical dissertation structure.
- (1) A title page, (2) a copyright page, (3) an abstract, (4) a dedication, (5) a statement of originality and acknowledgements, (6) a table of contents, (7) the**

¹⁰ Kate L. Turabian et al. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Styles for Students and Researchers*. Ninth Edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 141-146.

lists of abbreviations, (8) the lists of tables, (9) the lists of figures, (10) a dissertation chapter with an Introductory chapter, a literature review chapter, the methodology and methods' chapter, the results or findings section, the discussion of results' chapter, the conclusion with the statement of limitations and recommendations, the references, and the appendices.¹¹

- (1) A title page, (2) a copyright page, (3) an abstract, (4) a dedication, (5) a statement of originality and acknowledgements, (7) a table of contents, (8) the lists of abbreviations, (9) the lists of tables, (10) the lists of figures, (11) a dissertation chapter with an Introductory chapter, a literature review chapter, the result or findings section, the methodology and methods' chapter, the discussion of results' chapter, the conclusion with the statement of limitations and recommendations, the references, and the appendices.
- (1) A title page, (2) a copyright page, (3) an abstract, (4) a dedication, (5) a statement of originality and acknowledgements, (6) the lists of abbreviations, (7) the lists of tables, (8) the lists of figures, (9) a table of contents, (10) and a dissertation chapter with an Introductory chapter, a literature review chapter, the methodology and methods' chapter, the results or findings section, the discussion of results' chapter, the conclusion with the statement of limitations and recommendations, the references, and the appendices.
- (1) A title page, (2) a copyright page, (3) an abstract, (4) a dedication, (5) a statement of originality and acknowledgements, (6) a table of contents, (7) the lists

¹¹ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation*, 61-93.

of abbreviations, (8) the lists of tables, (9) the lists of figures, (10) and a dissertation chapter with an Introductory chapter, the methodology and methods' chapter, a literature review chapter, the results or findings section, the discussion of results' chapter, the conclusion with the statement of limitations and recommendations, the references, and the appendices.

12. Give the difference between the Notes Style and the Author-Date Style.

- In notes-style citations, you signal that you have used a source by placing a superscript number at the end of the sentence in which you quote it or refer to it: you then cite the source of that quotation in a correspondingly numbered note that provides information about the source (author, title, and facts of publication) plus relevant page numbers whereas, in the author-date citations, you signal that you have used a source by placing a parenthetical citation (including author, date, and relevant page numbers) next to your reference to it.¹²**
- In the author-date style citations, you signal that you have used a source by placing a superscript number at the end of the sentence in which you quote it or refer to it. In contrast, in notes-style citations, you signal that you have used a source by placing a parenthetical citation (including author, date, and relevant page numbers) next to your reference to it.

¹² Kate L. Turabian et al, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 141-142.

- In the author-date citations, you then cite the source of that quotation in a correspondingly numbered note that provides information about the source (author, title, and facts of publication) plus relevant page numbers. In contrast, in notes-style citations, you list all sources at the end of the paper.
- In notes-style citations, the reference list typically includes every source you cited in a parenthetical citation and sometimes others you consulted but did not cite. The publication date immediately follows the author's name. The author-date citations list typically includes every source you cited in a note and sometimes others you consulted but did not.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Adu, Philip. *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study*. YouTube 7 March 2016. Video, 1:05:16, accessed 20 April 2023, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708>.
- Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. The fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.
- Ellory Wells. Grammarly: How Good Is It and Is It Worth the Money? (YouTube Video, 15 November 2015, 21:47, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WSaOCIkpwP4&t=14s>).
- Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Styles for Students and Researchers*. The ninth edition revised by Wayne C. Boot, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. William, Joseph Bizup, and William T. Fitzgerald. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff, 2018.
- World Health Organization. *WHO style guide*. The second edition. Geneva: World Health Organization Publications, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.